

Security Risk Assessment Framework for Offshore Gas and Oil Platform in East Africa

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The global economy relies heavily on the offshore petroleum industry. Many nation-states regard offshore petroleum installations to be important national infrastructure, and their security could have substantial ramifications for national security and economic well-being. The major goal of this project is to develop a risk assessment technique for offshore platforms in order to help East African decision-makers. This is accomplished through a thorough evaluation of linked risks, as well as a review of relevant literature and traditional safety assessment methods, all of which lead to the development of a new knowledge-based risk assessment approach via the research methodology process. The study technique necessitates the gathering of data, which in this case was gathered from the industry. Surveys, visits, interviews, and questionnaires are among the data sources used to gather the information needed to test the model and conduct preliminary validation studies on offshore platform risk assessment in order to draw some conclusions.

Keywords: SECURITY RISK ASSESSMENT; OFFSHORE PETROLEUM INDUSTRY; EAST AFRICA

1.1 Research Overview

In this context, risk analysis can be defined as the study of the repercussions of security and engineering system failures in terms of potential harm to people, environmental damage, or property damage, including financial assets. Given the scope of the offshore security issues, risk assessments necessitate ongoing activities targeted at removing or

lowering threats. In this case, the role of safety analysis will primarily focus on the prevention, mitigation, or management of hazards throughout the project's life cycle. This falls within the umbrella of risk management. Risk management, on the other hand, is not about eliminating risks; rather, it is about encouraging an explicit decision-making process that will be utilized to limit the possible effects of specific risks and expedite project approvals. The experts on risk are unified in their belief that software-only solutions to the risk management

challenge are insufficient. Risk is defined as the prospect of economic or financial loss or gain, physical harm or injury, or delay as a result of the uncertainty involved with pursuing a certain course of action. More risk management innovation may be required because of this.

This management will include risk analysis as a means of stimulating the inventive deployment of diverse techniques, not only to conduct systematic analysis procedures, but also to deal with the uncertainty issues associated with risk data. The risk identification, evaluation, control, recommendation, and implementation processes are all part of this process. The various risk assessment methodologies based on current experiences have yielded more significant advances and will provide greater long-term advantages to the sector. In light of the foregoing, risk analysis approaches are increasingly being used to assess risk and reduce losses in a variety of industries, including railways, nuclear power, chemical processing, oil and gas, and so on.

2.1 Perspective of Risk Management

Though the above-mentioned risk management principles are relatively new, the risk at work literature dates back for further. In the 1920s, Herbert Heinrich, one of the country's early safety thinkers, conducted a study of the direct and indirect costs of workplace accidents, identifying the existence of a linear relationship and publishing a survey result on the relative frequency ratio of various types of accidents, including a popular "accident pyramid." Following that, many investigations were undertaken in order to better understand the relationship between serious and minor accidents.

The majority of current risk management models are based on quality and environmental management systems. Hazard identification and assessment, established rules and procedures, training, and a commitment to risk monitoring and mitigation are just a few of the key elements of proactive safety management. This can only be accomplished when clear policy goals and objectives, as well as a dedicated action plan, are in place. Other important factors include an effective communication mechanism, a well-defined structure, and clearly defined and specific responsibilities. This safety management model developed by the UK HSE is based on universal concepts and includes the basic five key elements.

2.2 Offshore Security Threats

Offshore oil and gas installations being attacked is not a new occurrence. There have been around 50 attacks and security problems affecting offshore installations in the last 25 years. These were carried out by a variety of criminals, each with their own reasons, goals, techniques, and capabilities. Terrorists, insurgents, pirates, criminal gangs, environmentalists, anti-oil activists, and other forms of demonstrators, hostile Nation-States, and occasionally other unknown groups and individuals are among them. Offshore security threats are activities that put offshore oil and gas installations' operations in jeopardy. An 'offshore security threat' is defined as any unlawful interference with offshore oil and gas operations or an act of violence directed at offshore infrastructure. Offshore security hazards can be characterized in a variety of ways based on a variety

of factors. A geographical classification, such as local or global, national, or transnational, is one example. Individuals or groups within or outside of a state, or a combination of both, may be the source of the attacks. The following are a few of the threat categories:

1. Piracy,
2. Terrorism
3. Insurgency
4. Organized Crime,
5. Civil protest
6. Inter-state hostilities
7. Vandalism
8. Internal sabotage

2.3 Risk Rating

After learning about offshore security risks and their characteristics, it's time to evaluate the level of danger each category of offshore security threats poses to offshore installations. The hazards posed by offshore security threats, as well as their risk assessments, are summarized in Table 1-1. Insurgency and terrorism are the most serious dangers to offshore petroleum installations, as seen in the table.

Table 1-1: Importance of Risk Ratings

Event ID	Fussell-Vesely	Birnbaum	Barlow-Prochain	Sequential	Risk Reduction Worth	Risk Achievement Worth
PIRACY	0.3504	1	0.3504	0	1.539	1.343
INTERNAL SABOTAGE	0.2699	1	0.2699	0	1.37	1.423
CIVIL PROTEST	0.2338	1	0.2338	0	1.305	1.459
INTERNAL HOSTILITIES	0.1386	1	0.1386	0	1.161	1.554
TERRORISM	0	1	0.3887	0	1	1.693
VANDALISM	0	1	0.3273	0	1	1.693
ORGANISED CRIME	0	1	0.3392	0	1	1.693
INSURGENCY	0	1	0.3504	0	1	1.693

2.4 Summary of Security Risk Assessment

To summarize the risk assessment all the parameters are discussed in three main points. The summarized data is shown in Table 1-2.

Table 1-2: Summary of Risk Assessment

Parameter	Point Value	Confidence Mean	Confidence (+) 90%
Unavailability	0.8417	0.8417	0.8417

Frequency	2.886	2.886	2.886
CFI	18.23	18.23	18.23
Number expected failures	311.5		
Unreliability	1		
MTTF	0.05385		
MTBF	0.3465		
MTTR	0.2916		
Total down time	83.75		
Mean unavailability	0.8375		
Risk reduction factor	1.194		
Q/T	0.008417		
Used method	Cross product		
Number of compact sets	8		

3.1 Methodology

The case study research approach was employed to assess two offshore major overhaul projects for this report. The data collecting and analysis approach was used only for the preparation and execution phases, as stated in the introductory section. The following steps were used to assess case studies:

1. Short introduction to the project was given.
2. A methodology matrix of the particular risk assessment process was shown.
3. A risk category map was made.

3.2 Case Studies

The scope and investment limitations were taken from the same initial planning preparation technique in both cases, and the period of execution was done in the same time frame and with most of the requisite resources found in house. On these two projects, separate risk management and analysis were carried out, even though the overhaul, investment and quality, budget, and time criteria were all the same, but the risk assessment was different. These case studies will be discussed in depth. Most risk assessments are related to the planning or execution phase, particularly in the areas of contingency, budget, quality, and activity durations. Both initiatives took a straightforward approach. The risk profile was divided into four categories based on the activities of the group: schedule, cost, quality, and performance. The scheduling was done with MS Project, and the risk workshop served as a kickoff for the risk and analysis strategy. The risk management tools utilised the standard identification and mitigation template components, as well as an early determined cost and likelihood matrix. Where it leads us to the project's results, including the overall risk management picture, contingency allocation, and final contingency spending

4.1 Risk Management

Risk management was well performed on the existing project. Identification of all major risks that emanated on the oil and gas projects was conducted via risk management analysis, risk assessment process and risk category map. In the early stage of project preparation, an initial risk assessment was conducted where it came to the agreement that risk management is needed. All project-related conditions that have the capability to prevent the impact of undesirable consequences on projects goals were conducted to uncover the weaknesses in development phase as in execution phase.

Figure 1: Reduced Risk Management Process

The overall risk assessment approach employed in this project is depicted in Figure 1. The system was built around the following subprocesses: launching the risk system, identifying risk, consulting with, and communicating with the Functional Area Managers (FAMs), analyzing the risk, evaluating risk, treating risk, preparing the contingency report, and finally controlling and monitoring risk-related events. If the regulating measures are not followed, the risk must go through the process depicted in Figure 2. The recommendation was to assign the risks based on their repercussions on a project, through an approach of the risk source allocation and the amount of knowledge, in order to build an appropriate risk categorization system for construction projects. Each of them must meet the following criteria known knowns, known unknowns, unknown knowns, and unknown unknowns. The technique yielded the benefit of separating risk from the likelihood of risk occurring.

Figure 2: Risk Assessment Process

The present project's risk management was only partially completed. Some of the project aspects depicted in Figures 3 and 4 underwent risk and analysis preparation, and the majority of them appear to agree with case study A. As a result, risk management is about identifying the sources of project risks and determining techniques to lean toward common practices for mitigating missing stages on projects using a contingency approach. All project-related major group risk categories were presented in case study A, where they were threatened by the entire risk assessment, whereas in case study B, the major group risk categories' conditions were lowered.

The risk-reduced assessment process is depicted in Figure 2. The system is set up at the level of a few fundamental sub-processes, with the risk management approach adopted from the standpoint of substantial contingency reserves if the majority of the identified hazards occur. Due to previous performance experience, the need for a fast-track pace in the preparation or execution phase, and a general risk strategy, certain elements appearing in procedure A were left out of procedure B. The next step was to figure out whether this would be

done qualitatively or quantitatively, using a conventional risk matrix and experience. To stick with the reduced risk categories strategy, the majority of the general hazards should be assigned to risk classification based on knowledge level. As a knowledge decision, employing a quantitative general model approach to risk and analysis assessment and selective qualitative analysis in chosen risk areas by contributing missing assessments by contingency incense is offered. In case study B, a model is built based on expert qualitative analysis, with the contingency taken to mitigate the unpredictable forms of risks associated with mandated or planned modifications that occur on projects owing to external and internal influences. One of the critical links was the knowledge risks method, which was used in some risk system areas where there was a risk of important employees departing the project, posing a significant risk to the existing general quantitative approach evaluation. This notion is founded on the evident reality that the risk management method in case study B will have to cope with the longest feasible time required for project completion, as well as restricted resources with lower performance expertise and quality.

4.2 Registry of Risk

As previously stated, the risk system's major goal is to begin with the identification phase in order to build a risk register of project-specific risks per segment as well as the risk map specified in case study A. The risk register for Case Study A provides a list of conventional hazards that are employed in all overhaul construction projects, as well as the risks that apply to the project's specific deviation segments and outside drivers. Over 100 probable harmful occurrences have been discovered in a detailed, thorough list of all dangers. The risk register categorizes many significant dangers and assigns risk category ratings to each of them. The risk register was designed to take a more restricted view of a realistic risk, based on subject matter experts' recommendations, consultations, and FAMS. By allocating resources to all phases of the assessment and actions, the identification process strategy presented in Case Study 1 was able to produce a narrow key risk register with no missing pieces in the process. If noncritical risks are recognized while some of the most critical risks are overlooked, the risk analysis approach may lead decision makers in the wrong direction, causing the risk register to be misled.

Figure 3: Risk category contingency realization

Figure 4: Risk category contingency realization

Figures 3 and 4 were created using risk response strategies that maximized the risk response effects of adopting mitigating elements. The probability matrix is defined from the low-low / low / medium / high / high-high risk level on the combined graphic, which shows the 10 primary group risk categories. Following the risk assessment, the mitigation curve was relocated to the lower level of potential risks, and some related probability cost was added, as shown in Figure 1. The holistic strategy was taken from the perspective of risk management,

where the mitigation was done meticulously, and the risk flow level showed immediate progress. Because of the good mitigation plan, a contingency was established on the level that the least cost, cost table will be related.

Figure 5: Risk category contingency realization

Figure 6: Risk category contingency realization

Due to the reduced risk management approach Figure 2, it is obvious from the above risk category map Figures 5 and 6 that in the groups, a large contingency is recorded. The overall impact of the contingency allocation between the groups is unknown, however contingency was determined for the three groups based on the average % safety contingency. Figures 5 and 6 were created using general risk response techniques organized by risk coping capacity and a paired effect on success. Through the key general group hazards categories, the response impacts of adopting mitigation while considering project cost of methods, project schedule, and project quality were done with the probability of maximizing related probability cost.

The combined chart depicts the seven key risk categories for groups. The mitigation curve was slightly adjusted to the lower level of the potential hazards where related probability cost was added after the decreased risk assessment was applied using the processes shown in Figure 2. The third-party external group's approach for the missing three risk category groupings was based on best knowledge and experience. The best practice

information was used in all other group assessments. This method leaves a comprehensive strategy out of the picture, even though mitigation variables can be detected. The combined chart depicts the seven key risk categories for groups. The mitigation curve was slightly adjusted to the lower level of the potential hazards where related probability cost was added after the decreased risk assessment was applied using the processes shown in Figure 2. The third-party external group's approach for the missing three risk category groupings was based on best knowledge and experience. The best practice information was used in all other group assessments. By taking this strategy, a full approach is lacking from the viewpoint, where even mitigating elements might be observed.

5.1 Discussing the Results

The research found that risk management is critical for successful project planning and execution, and that it should be implemented on a regular basis so that firms may accomplish their cost, schedule, and quality targets while adhering to the project's basic requirements and nature. This section outlines the most relevant findings from the two case studies that were conducted.

The risk management and analysis methods of one department have been established and are being carried out efficiently in the case study. Their procedures are in line with the company's own policies and procedures. The firm has a structured method for identifying risks, in which the departmental risk analysis is conducted in a deterministic manner, with detected risks being reviewed by the estimator responsible or jointly by the FAM's team in a risk conference. Both dangers and opportunities are reviewed during the meetings, with a distinct focus on the threats. The most important risks are recorded in a risk register, which includes both threats and opportunities. Unidentified risks and risks with minimal consequences are covered by a contingency cost, which is added to the risk register.

In case study 1, 60% of the contingency was preserved, which means that funds were not used and all deadlines were met. The data also imply that risk aversion and risk coping capacity have a direct impact on the success of project portfolios. In scenario 2, the contingency cost is also estimated informally based on past experiences and gut instinct. On the basis of the general methodology, major risk category regions were missed during the assessment. Competence risks were characterized as misleading and missing steps in the process, where the risks come because of inadequate project management competency. Misunderstandings and inaccuracies can result from ineffective communication between the FAMs at any level of the project or risk assessment. In case study 2, the contingency was employed to meet 80% of the deadlines. In case study 1, on the other hand, regardless of experience, the quantitative method was carried out by statistical analysis of historical data for the exact circumstance, with risk event prediction and risk parameter calculation.

6.1 Conclusion

Considering the two risk management methodologies discussed in case studies, it was determined that businesses utilize a standard risk management and analysis approach definition. The findings suggest that

organizations' or enterprises' expertise, or even their best practices, must have certain risk benchmarks and standard practice in place so that when a risk event occurs, the incorporated mitigation choices and risk analysis strategies produce the best answer. The definition and measurement magnitude, as well as the consequence and probability of risk events, all add up to the use of risk magnitude. During the risk management process, this critical shared risk definition technique reduces misconceptions and confusion. When comparing the cost of resources vs. the cost of not detecting possible risks, the project organization suffers greatly. As a result, on the majority of complicated projects, the core functions that make up the risk analysis or assessment technique must be applied.

The common risk strategy must be used to improve risk analysis/quantification and the adoption of a risk best practice structure at a minimum. Both internationally and internally, today's market is rapidly evolving. As a result, a risk-aware common structure is required to provide sufficient insight into a project's risk exposure. Using two risk registers, the common structure distinguishes risks from opportunities. Continuous risk management is the process of connecting the common current risk register with the new project approach's risk register. This method leads to a more probabilistic continuous risk management procedure.

References

1. A.M. Cruz, E. Krausmann, Damage to offshore oil and gas facilities following hurricanes Katrina and Rita: An overview, *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 21, Issue 6, 2008, 620-626
2. NORSOK, Risk and emergency preparedness assessment. NORSOK Standard Z-013. Edition 3, October 2010.
3. Reale and R. Atlas, 2001: Tropical Cyclone–Like Vortices in the Extratropics: Observational Evidence and Synoptic Analysis. *Wea. Forecasting*, 16, 7–34
4. PSA - Petroleum Safety Authority Norway (2014). Anchor line failure - Norwegian Continental Shelf - 2010-2014.
5. NPD - National Petroleum Directorate, 2016- http://gis.npd.no/factmaps/html_20/ (last access 25/08/2016), 209-215
6. OGP (2010), Consequence modelling, Risk Assessment Data Directory, Report No. 434-7 (March 2010)
7. Schuller J.C.H et.al (1997) Methods for determining and processing probabilities – the Red Book. Second Edition. Committee for Prevention of Disasters, The Netherlands. CPR 12E
8. J. F. Roberts, A. J. Champion, L. C. Dawkins, K. I. Hodges, L. C. Shaffrey, D. B. Stephenson, M. A. Stringer, H. E. Thornton, and B. D. Youngman, The XWS open access catalogue of extreme European windstorms from 1979 to 2012, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 14, 2487–2501, 2014
9. Kaiser M. J. World offshore energy loss statistics, *Energy Policy* 35, 2007, 3496-3525
10. Kushnir, Y., V. J. Cardone, J. G. Greenwood, and M. A. Cane, 1997: The recent increase in North Atlantic wave heights. *J. Climate*, 10, 2107–2113
11. PSA - Petroleum Safety Authority Norway (2014). Anchor line failure - Norwegian Continental Shelf - 2010-2014.
12. NPD - National Petroleum Directorate, 2016- http://gis.npd.no/factmaps/html_20/ (last access 25/08/2016), 209-215

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